

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF AI IN EFL TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract

This article explores the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and provides an overview of two innovative technologies: ChatGPT and Wordtune. ChatGPT offers an interactive environment for students to practice speaking in English through virtual dialogues, while Wordtune provides AI-assisted text rewriting. The article discusses the advantages and disadvantages of using technology in education, specifically AI, and its impact on learning. It emphasises the importance of balancing innovation with caution, ensuring human control and the development of critical thinking.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), EFL Teaching (English as a Foreign Language), ChatGPT, Wordtune, Language Learning Technologies, Educational Innovation, Language Proficiency Enhancement, AI Writing Tools, Pedagogical Applications, Ethical Implications

Education is becoming the primary location for experimentation and innovation due to the rapid evolution of technology. In particular, the field of teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) is at the forefront, utilizing cutting-edge technology, such as artificial intelligence (AI), to enhance learning outcomes. This paper delves into the role of AI in EFL instruction, focusing on two advanced technologies: Wordtune and ChatGPT. ChatGPT, a Generative-Transformative Networks (GPT) based technology, offers textual feedback through virtual dialogues, providing a unique learning experience. On the other hand, Wordtune, an AI-powered tool, offers text revision, alternative phrasing, and writing advice, boosting language competency and English writing skills. In this essay, we explore the practical applications of these technologies and their impact on teaching English to non-native speakers, improving language proficiency, and creating an engaging learning environment conducive to efficient language acquisition.

The use of AI-powered writing tools in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms is on the rise. In addition to grammar checks and writing aids, there are programs that will create a written work like an essay without requiring any human assistance. Their ease of use and effectiveness save students and educators both time and energy. Furthermore, AI writing tools have been used specifically for English as a foreign language learners with lower English proficiency. Students can obtain rapid feedback and support through the use of these tools, allowing them to detect and correct errors more quickly. Recently, there has been an increase in the number of viewpoints about how artificial intelligence affects pupils' writing skills. Others suggest that employing AI can assist students improve their writing skills, while others are concerned about the potential negative consequences of these tools. These include reliance on technology, safety concerns, a lack of empathy, and a lack of inventiveness. The Chat Bot is one example of innovation that is fast gaining popularity. Artificial intelligence (AI) has taken over the globe, and

its powers have been recognized by everyone from academics to ordinary Internet users. It is a component of artificial intelligence, which many people find fascinating. However, some educators are concerned about them. They've heard stories of cheating and bad behavior involving chat bots. Concerned about the usage of ChatGPT, educational institutions have declared a ban on its use one following another. Teachers and school administrators believe ChatGPT jeopardizes pupils' critical thinking and writing abilities. ChatGPT is a computer application that communicates with people in a way that feels natural. ChatGPT can converse with users in a natural and responsive manner. The language model's neural network, which employs vast data sets to construct varying strengths of connections, ensures that ChatGPT can generate textual responses similar to human speech, answer follow-up inquiries, admit mistakes, and so on. ChatGPT can additionally produce text in a wide range of formats such as essays, humor, and poetry. Its performance on similar tasks (e.g., answering similar questions) can be improved with continuing user interaction.

Essentially, contrary to widely held and frequently idealized notions, ChatGPT analyzes the available data to determine the most likely (i.e., most frequent and pertinent) answers to users' queries rather than reasoning or reacting emotionally. As a result, end-user feedback is critical to its eventual accuracy. ChatGPT is unable to "understand" the language it creates or the context of the information because of its underlying methodology, resulting in plausible-sounding yet inaccurate or nonsensical answers. . Scientists and media outlets have previously expressed worries regarding the correctness of material offered by ChatGPT, with some claiming that ChatGPT invents content in the face of a dearth of expertise and even fabricates phony sources. Experts discovered that, notwithstanding their apparent capability, chatbots do not understand the meaning of the words being proposed. To be more specific, ChatGPT is a new text-generating search tool that lacks the ability to search the Internet for pertinent content,

but it does an amazing job of simulating human interaction and filtering out superfluous information to propose what the user is looking for. It is, without a doubt, a really powerful search tool, but there is where it ends, reminding us of the same wonder we felt when we first used Google search or Google scholar. The prevalent uneasiness is largely the result of a lack of comprehension of technology, which leads to an anxiety of the unfamiliar. Texts generated by a chatbot using a big language model are easy to recognize at this stage because the writing style follows a pattern. This imagined level of capacity has prompted severe ethical issues concerning the use of GPT's future generation. According to Business Insider (2023), OpenAI CEO Sam Altman has stated that the next generation of GPT will not be distributed until they figure out how to utilize it securely and ethically. As long as then, second/foreign language educators have a bit of time to work over the issue of ethical and responsible usage of chatbots with students, discussing their benefits, challenges, and risks, which is a far better method than avoiding the matter totally.

ChatGPT provides numerous educational advantages and prospects. Some argue that experiential learning can assist learners since ChatGPT can generate various problem-solving scenarios. ChatGPT also offers individualized tutoring to students. AI labeling may alleviate educators of a hefty workload, permitting them to devote more time to lesson preparation. ChatGPT has a number of major advantages for students.

Because ChatGPT perfectly simulates human contact, students can quickly initiate an actual dialogue with the chatbot. The benefit of this is that students are usually asking genuine questions, especially when in search of projects to consider. As a result, all of the aspects required for an honest discussion will be present, such as summarizing, asking subsequent inquiries, clarifying, sharing information, and so on. Unlike most classroom sessions, students receive chance to work on many areas of language use. Above all else, ChatGPT is unique in that it provides users with a plethora of academic resources and materials. Many of the platforms or programs previously utilized by students, such as Grammarly, Wikipedia, Google Translate, Quillbot, and so on, are used in tandem by ChatGPT. As a result, he is able to recognize language and organizational issues in pupils' writing, as well as suggest writing ideas

and make adjustments. He can also explain and provide examples of how to use terminology. Most significantly, advice is instantaneous, as opposed to instructor feedback, which takes time and might have completely lost whatever was previously written by the time students receive feedback.

Due to ChatGPT is unavoidable, educators and institutions should seize the chance to innovate traditional teaching and evaluation approaches. To begin, SL/FL teachers should minimize the quantity of take-home tasks, which they ought to be doing, because long-standing market tools like Google Translate and Quillbot have eroded the genuineness and reliability of numerous of these assignments. Where take-home projects need to be provided, teachers could offer activities that AI chatbots cannot readily do, such as composing daily diary entries, summarizing lecture content, or other forms of written assignments. Although ChatGPT offers various opportunities for significant changes in education, there are numerous unknown consequences and prospective repercussions that require additional exploration. [1]

Wordtune is a second popular AI writing tool. Wordtune is an artificial intelligence-powered digital writing helper that can alter the chosen content through modifying the structure of sentences or replacement words with synonyms while retaining the original meaning. Machine learning is used in this technology to train a machine to interpret and build natural text from enormous amounts of written material. Wordtune, which is powered by artificial intelligence, recognizes trends in a huge dataset and provides possibilities for creating unique phrases rather than stealing text from other web sources.

Wordtune can be accessed via its own online writer or as a browser extension. As a browser extension, the program works with a variety of online services, including Gmail, Google Docs, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, WhatsApp (web version), Slack, and others. Once installed to the browser, users can write in any compatible web application. Let's go over the way to use Wordtune. Above the selected text, a purple circle with a "W" will emerge. Users can get a list of choices for altering the highlighted text by clicking on this icon. Wordtune offers a variety of rewriting options, such as basic rewriting, informal tone, formal tone, reduced text, and extended text. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. An example of a rewrite suggestion via Wordtune (formal tone).

Wordtune is only accessible for English writing at the moment, although it is capable of translating content from various languages into English (Figure 2). This translation option is very helpful for EFL authors

who type an expression or section of a phrase in a different language and then choose the content to receive English rephrasing possibilities. The translation feature is available in Spanish, Mandarin, Arabic, Hindi, Korean, Hebrew, and Russian.

Figure 2. An example of the translation feature of Wordtune.

Wordtune is a handy tool for improving the level of quality of what you write in real time. It is appropriate for users with varying levels of knowledge of English. In this regard, the interpreting function is especially valuable for English novices who face a language barrier. Such users may also produce rewriting or paraphrasing choices in English based on an English sentence composed of many terms from their original language (Figure 3). Instead of being caught on a single phrase or expression, the technology will assist them in

maintaining a continual flow of English texts. Artificial intelligence-generated rewriting choices will assist users improve their English by proposing relevant synonyms, deleting wrong words, and selecting a desired tone for advanced English writers who want to write at a more sophisticated level. Users can also use the text shortening and lengthening functions to make content more compact or to produce more thoughts. Wordtune provides options for self-directed learning for EFL writers, but it can also be valuable from a pedagogical

standpoint. Teachers, for example, might organize web-based writing assignments and encourage students to utilize Wordtune during the writing process. Teachers should also encourage participants to recollect on

what they have learned from participating in the revisions, such as new words, synonyms, clauses, and professional form of sentences that they would not have been able to utilize in their writing otherwise.

Figure 3. An example of the translation feature of Wordtune.

Wordtune and ChatGPT are two examples of artificial intelligence technologies that are becoming more and more recognized as significant assistants in the writing process. Wordtune acts as an effective writing aid, suggesting various ways to improve and enhance what we write. It is a helpful tool, especially when it comes to developing thoughts or selecting the most relevant words or phrases. ChatGPT, on the other hand, is renowned for its ability to emulate mental processes and conversational abilities, despite being incredibly sophisticated. Teachers frequently expose students to ChatGPT, recognizing its utility but cautioning them about its faults, such as its lack of human interaction and logic. By reconsidering old ways to learning, the development of machine learning in education has resulted in about dramatic change. Despite reservations regarding the utilization of artificial intelligence for knowledge and the risk of misunderstandings, there is an urgent need to strike a balance. It is vital to capitalize

on technology improvements while exercising caution in their deployment. The use of AI technologies like ChatGPT and Wordtune deserves to be addressed with caution, emphasizing the significance of control from humans and critical thinking skills in conjunction with dependence on technology. This well-rounded strategy is required to maximize the positive effects of AI-based learning while minimizing its inherent hazards. [2]

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